

¹H-NMR Study of Some Substituted Acetophenones and Aryl Methyl Sulphoxides : Evidence for Steric Enhancement of Resonance

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Manuscript received 19 June 1982, revised 17 May 1983, accepted 1 September 1983

From the proton magnetic resonance chemical shift of the ω -methyl groups of certain substituted acetophenones and aryl methyl sulphoxides, evidence for steric enhancement of resonance is furnished. The chemical shift value of ω -methyl groups of 4-methoxyacetophenone, 4-methylthioacetophenone and 4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide gets shifted upfield due to greater shielding when there is any substituent at 3-position of the phenyl ring. The extent of shielding seems to be proportional to the bulkiness of the group *ortho* to the methoxy or the methylthio group.

THE mesomeric conjugation of methoxyl group with phenyl ring is increased if there is any substituent *ortho* to it. This phenomenon is termed as steric enhancement of resonance¹. Since its discovery, several physico-chemical investigations such as reactivity²⁻⁸, magnetic susceptibilities⁹, dissociation constants¹⁰, polarographic and spectral¹¹ studies have been carried out in support of this phenomenon. Recently, we analysed¹² the ultraviolet and infrared spectral data of some suitably substituted aryl methyl sulphoxides and found that the conjugation of 4-methoxyl group gets increased when there is a substituent in 3-position and gets decreased if there are two substituents at 3- and 5-positions. In the present paper we report the proton magnetic resonance spectral data of some substituted acetophenones and aryl methyl sulphoxides as an additional evidence for steric enhancement of resonance.

Experimental

All the substituted acetophenones and aryl methyl sulphoxides were prepared and purified as described earlier^{6,13}. The nmr spectrum of each compound was recorded on Perkin Elmer model R 32 NMR spectrometer, operating at 90 MHz, in carbon tetrachloride using tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Since we are interested only in the chemical shift values of the functional groups, attention has not been paid for analysing phenyl protons.

Results and Discussion

The chemical shift values of all the acetophenones are given in Table 1. The proton signal of ω -methyl group of acetophenone appears at 2.5 δ . The ω -methyl protons of acetophenone absorb at much lower field than would be predicted on grounds of electronegativity or a simple atomic

diamagnetic effect, because of the orientation of the carbonyl group such that the plane of the trigonal carbon atom is perpendicular to the field. Thus, there is diamagnetic circulations in the carbonyl group producing an anisotropic effect which results in deshielding. On the basis of the theories of magnetic shielding it is suggested that the structural features are expected to contribute to the chemical shift of the ω -methyl protons. The shielding of a specific nucleus is considered to be due to two major factors, (a) the electron density about the nucleus and (b) the presence of magnetically anisotropic groupings within the molecule. In the case of acetophenone, the anisotropic carbonyl group

TABLE 1—PROTON MAGNETIC RESONANCE SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME ACETOPHENONES

Substituent	Chemical shift δ			
	ω -CH ₃	3-CH ₃	3,5-di- CH ₃	4-OCH ₃
None	2.5	—	—	—
3-Methyl	2.6	2.2	—	—
3-Fluoro	2.5	—	—	—
3-Chloro	2.5	—	—	—
3-Bromo	2.6	—	—	—
3-Iodo	2.6	—	—	—
4-Methoxy	2.4	—	—	3.8
4-Methylthio	2.4	—	—	2.1*
4-Methoxy-3-methyl	2.0	2.5	—	3.8
3-Fluoro-4-methoxy	2.2	—	—	4.0
3-Chloro-4-methoxy	2.1	—	—	4.0
3-Bromo-4-methoxy	2.0	—	—	4.0
3-Iodo-4-methoxy	1.8	—	—	3.9
3-Methyl-4-methylthio	2.1	2.2	—	2.4*
3-Chloro-4-methylthio	2.4	—	—	2.3*
3-Bromo-4-methylthio	2.3	—	—	2.2*
3,5-Dimethyl-4-methoxy	2.6	—	2.7	3.8
3,5-Dichloro-4-methoxy	2.6	—	—	4.0
3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxy	2.6	—	—	4.0
3,5-Diiodo-4-methoxy	2.7	—	—	4.0
3,5-Dimethyl-4-methylthio	2.6	—	2.3	2.4*

* Chemical shift value for 4-methylthio protons.

and the aromatic ring would be expected to have pronounced effects on chemical shifts.

For protons, the electron distribution about the nucleus is essentially isotropic and the local effect, (a) above, is diamagnetic and directly dependent on the electron density. Therefore, the greater the electron density, the greater will be the shielding, due to the circulation of electrons surrounding a specific proton. So it is suggested that the chemical shift of the ω -methyl protons will be determined only by the relative magnitudes of the electronic influence of substituents in the phenyl ring of acetophenone since it may be assumed that the deshielding effect of the carbonyl group will be approximately the same in all the cases. As a first approximation, however, it seems reasonable to assume that the ring effect remains virtually constant as the ω -methyl group is far removed from the aromatic nucleus.

Since an electron-releasing substituent would tend to decrease the positive nature of the carbonyl group, the shift of ω -methyl protons in such a system would be expected to be towards higher field, while electron-withdrawing substituent would tend to produce the opposite effect. The chemical shift values of *m*-methyl protons and ω -methyl protons of 3-methylacetophenone are 2.2 and 2.5 δ , respectively. Due to the presence of a methyl group at 3-position of acetophenone there seems to be no difference in the absorption for the ω -methyl group. But, when there is methoxyl group at 4-position of acetophenone the value gets decreased by one unit compared with that of acetophenone, due to the electron-releasing nature of methoxyl group. The value gets still decreased in the case of 4-methoxy-3-methylacetophenone. This considerable decrease in the absorption position is ascribed to the steric enhancement of resonance as follows:

Fig. 1

The methyl group *ortho* to the methoxyl group restricts the rotation of the methoxyl group about the C—O axis. The $-\text{OCH}_3$ group takes up the preferred orientation, anti to *ortho* methyl group. This increases the overlap between the lone pair orbital of oxygen and p-orbital of aromatic carbon. This in turn enhances the conjugative interaction between the methoxyl group and acetyl function. Thus the enhanced mesomeric interaction greatly shields the ω -methyl protons.

Again, the presence of fluoro-, chloro-, bromo- and iodo-substituents at 3-position of acetophenone does not alter the chemical shift value of ω -methyl protons considerably. This could be an indication that the *meta* substituents exert a small effect through space. But if they are present *ortho* to methoxyl group, considerable decrease in the chemical shift value of ω -methyl protons is noticed. Actually the corresponding values for 3-fluoro-

4-methoxyacetophenone (2.2 δ), 3-chloro-4-methoxyacetophenone (2.1 δ), 3-bromo-4-methoxyacetophenone (2.0 δ) and 3-iodo-4-methoxyacetophenone (1.8 δ) are in accordance with the expectation. The gradual decrease of ω - CH_3 chemical shift value from 2.2 to 1.8 δ , as we go from fluoro to iodo groups, is due to the bulk effect. As the size of the halogen atom increases, the extent of mesomeric interaction of methoxyl group with the acetyl function also increases due to steric operation. It is interesting that the shifts to higher field increase with the increase in the size of the substituent.

The chemical shift value of ω -methyl group of 3,5-dimethyl-4-methoxyacetophenone, 3,5-dichloro-4-methoxyacetophenone, 3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyacetophenone and 3,5-diiodo-4-methoxyacetophenone are almost the same and seem to be slightly higher than that of 4-methoxyacetophenone. In these cases the phenomenon of steric inhibition of resonance is found to operate. The two O,O'-substituents force the methoxyl group to take non-planar orientation with respect to the plane of the benzene ring, thus reducing its conjugative interaction with the acetyl group. The overlap of the lone pair orbital of oxygen and p-orbital of aromatic carbon is decreased to a minimum and hence lesser shielding.

The chemical shift value of ω -methyl group of 4-methylthioacetophenone is seen to be identical with that of 4-methoxyacetophenone. If it happens to be *ortho* to methyl group or halogens its resonance interaction with acetyl group is increased (Fig. 2). For 3-methyl-4-methylthioacetophenone,

Fig. 2

the ω -methyl proton shift value is 2.1 δ which is less than that of 4-methylthioacetophenone. This low value is due to steric enhancement of resonance. 3-Chloro-4-methylthioacetophenone and 3-bromo-4-methylthioacetophenone have the ω -methyl chemical shift values at 2.4 and 2.3 δ , respectively. Here again as the size of the halogen atom increases, the chemical shift value of the ω -methyl protons decreases showing greater resonance interaction of methylthio group when it is *ortho* to halogens.

3,5-Dimethyl-4-methylthioacetophenone has its ω -methyl chemical shift at 2.6 δ which is higher than that of 4-methylthioacetophenone, due to steric inhibition of resonance. The relative enhancement of resonance is seen more in the case of methoxyl group compared with methylthio group. This may be due to the varying electron-releasing capacity of $-\text{OCH}_3$ and $-\text{SCH}_3$ groups. Because of the difference in the primary quantum number between the lone pair electrons (3P) of sulphur and the aromatic π -electrons (2P), the mesomeric electron-release from the substituent to the ring is less important for sulphur than for oxygen. The

variation in the chemical shift values of 3-methyl, 4-methoxyl and 4-methylthio protons in various compounds do not follow any regular trend (see Table 1).

A similar effect of the steric enhancement of resonance is also observed in suitably substituted aryl methyl sulphoxides. The observed spectral data are listed in Table 2. The chemical shift value of ω -methyl group of methyl phenyl sulphoxide appears at 3.0 δ . 3-Methylphenyl methyl sulphoxide and 4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide have their corresponding values at 2.9 and 2.8 δ , respectively. 3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide has a low value at 2.4 δ . This lowering in the value of the chemical shift is due to the involvement of more conjugative interaction of $-\text{SOCH}_3$ group with $-\text{OCH}_3$ group which is sterically made more favourable for resonance interaction by the presence of 3-methyl group. Similarly, chloro or bromo substituent at 3-position makes the 4-methoxyl group to be in higher degree of resonance interaction with $-\text{SOCH}_3$ group. Hence the chemical shift value of the ω -methyl group of 3-chloro-4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide and 3-bromo-4-methoxy-

phenyl methyl sulphoxide appears at 2.6 and 2.5 δ , respectively.

The ω -methyl protons of 3,5-dimethyl-4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide and 3,5-dichloro-4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide resonate at 2.8 and 2.9 δ , respectively. These values are higher than that of 4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide due to steric inhibition of resonance. However, they are less than that of methyl phenyl sulphoxide because of the substituent effect of two methyl groups or two chloro substituents, and a fraction of the effect of methoxyl group may still operate.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance to one of the authors (M.R.) by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, in the form of a Senior Research Fellowship is gratefully acknowledged.

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TABLE 2—PROTON MAGNETIC RESONANCE SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME ARLY METHYL SULPHOXIDES

Substituent	Chemical shift δ			
	ω -CH ₃	3-CH ₃	3,5-di- CH ₃	4-OCH ₃
None	3.0	—	—	—
3-Methyl	2.9	2.2	—	—
3-Chloro	3.2	—	—	—
3-Bromo	3.1	—	—	—
4-Methoxy	2.8	—	—	4.3
4-Methoxy-3-methyl	2.4	2.1	—	4.0
3-Chloro-4-methoxy	2.6	—	—	4.1
3-Bromo-4-methoxy	2.5	—	—	3.9
3,5-Dimethyl-4-methoxy	2.8	—	2.4	3.8
3,5-Dichloro-4-methoxy	2.9	—	—	4.0